

Metal Volume Fraction Approach for Fiber/Metal Laminates

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents results of a statistically designed program conducted to validate feasibility of using the relationship of mechanical properties and metal volume fraction in fiber/metal laminates to make property predictions. Experimental and analytical practices employed to obtain these mechanical properties for tension, compression, in-plane shear, and bearing are described. Results from this pilot study conclude that use of metal volume fraction may be useful for the prediction of strength mechanical properties in fiber/metal laminates. However, this needs further study to validate the concept. If the hypothesis is valid, the number of laminate configurations to be tested to qualify a fiber/metal laminate family can be minimized. The findings imply that metal volume fraction approach using a rule-of-mixtures can be exploited to estimating design properties for a multitude of fiber/metal laminate variants, which is economically beneficial to preliminary stages of aircraft design.

KEY WORDS: Fiber/metal laminates, metal fraction, rule-of-mixtures, experimental design, tension, compression, in-plane shear, bearing, fiber orientation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber/metal laminates are engineered materials composed of thin structural sheet metal plies alternatively bonded to plies of fiber-reinforced polymer. Such hybrid materials combine the best features of the metal and fiber-reinforced composite of which they are composed. Fiber/metal laminates retain the conventional workshop practices of metals, including damage inspectability [1-5]. These attributes alone dramatically reduce the implementation cost associated with application of fiber/metal laminates. Fiber/metal laminates, ARALL (Kevlar fiber-based aluminum laminates) or GLARE (S-2 glass fiber-based aluminum laminates), are particularly promising for aerospace structural applications, where the qualities of low weight [6, 7], high strength/stiffness, and good damage tolerance are essential. In addition, fiber/metal laminates also exhibit good thermal stability in cryogenic and elevated temperature environments [8-10].

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Although ARALL 2 and ARALL 3 laminate design allowables [11] have currently been accepted for incorporation into a newly written Chapter of MIL-HDBK-5, *Miscellaneous Alloys and Hybrid Materials*, the case of GLARE laminates is more complex due to their composite prepreg lay-up configurations. To enable the usage of GLARE laminates in multiple applications in aerospace industry, especially for fuselage application, it is necessary to qualify a broad family of fiber/metal laminates according to MIL-HDBK-5 requirements. However, if the qualification procedure is based on the testing of individual configuration, financial constraints will limit the number of configurations that can be qualified. A possible solution for this dilemma is the applicability of the metal volume fraction approach using the rule-of-mixtures (ROM) to predict properties. If the hypothesis of this pilot study is correct, then the MIL-HDBK-5 design properties of different laminate configurations can be predicted as a function of their metal volume fraction, the qualification of fiber/metal laminate family only requires a minimum testing effort on a few laminate configurations.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

The hypothesis considered is that mechanical properties of hybrid laminates, such as ultimate strength and modulus, can be predicted by the ROM. In carrying out the analysis, individual identities of fiber and matrix are ignored. Each individual layer of laminate (aluminum alloy or composite layer) is treated as a homogeneous, orthotropic sheet and the laminated hybrid material is analyzed using the classical theory of laminated plates. These are:

For ultimate strength,

$$\sigma_{lam} = V_{al} \times \sigma_{al} + (1 - V_{al}) \times \sigma_p \quad (1)$$

For Young's modulus,

$$E_{lam} = V_{al} \times E_{al} + (1 - V_{al}) \times E_p \quad (2)$$

For in-plane shear modulus,

$$1/G_{lam} = V_{al}/G_{al} + (1 - V_{al})/G_p \quad (3)$$

where

- σ_{lam} = laminate ultimate strength
- σ_{al} = aluminum alloy ultimate strength
- σ_p = cured composite prepreg ultimate strength
- E_{lam} = Young's modulus of the laminate
- E_{al} = Young's modulus of the aluminum alloy
- E_p = Young's modulus of the cured composite prepreg
- G_{lam} = shear modulus of the laminate
- G_{al} = shear modulus of the aluminum alloy
- G_p = shear modulus of the cured composite prepreg
- V_{al} = aluminum alloy volume fraction.

3. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Material

Laminate configurations of 2/1, 3/2, and 5/4 were considered. In definition, for example, 3/2 GLARE 4 consists of three layers of 0.012-in. (or 0.016-in) thick aluminum alloy sheets and two layers of 70/30 glass prepreg (with 70% of fibers in 0° orientation and 30% of fibers in 90° orientation in each glass prepreg). Each prepreg layer (0°/90°/0°) has a 0.015-in. thickness. A GLARE 4 laminate schematic representation is shown in Figure 1. The use of GLARE 4 laminates allows the evaluation of bi-axial laminates and will give maximum information for the longitudinal (L) and long-transverse (LT) testing direction. To examine the variability of the metal volume fraction approach, five panels of different laminate configurations were evaluated. Two standard aluminum alloy sheet thicknesses, 0.012-in. and 0.016-in., were used for controlling desired metal volume fraction. Type of lay-up, total laminate thickness, and metal volume fraction are listed in Table 1.

3.2 Experimental Design

In this pilot study, static design properties were evaluated using a simple statistically designed experiment as described in Reference 12. Mechanical property determinations include the tensile ultimate and yield strengths, compressive yield strength, in-plane shear yield strength, and bearing ultimate and yield strengths. In addition, tensile, compressive, and in-plane shear moduli are also of interest. In this experimental program, quadruplicate tests were performed in both the L and LT directions, executed according to the run order provided in Reference 12. Two randomizations were involved in carrying out these experiments. The first was the random assignment of the treatment variables to the specimens cut from each panel. This was done to guard against systematic variations in the properties of the material with position on the panel. The second randomization involved testing the samples in a random time order. This guarded against a systematic drift in the testing system with time. Tension, compression, and bearing tests were carried out in Delft University and in-plane shear tests were performed at the Alcoa Technical Center.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metal volume fraction is the fractional quantity of aluminum alloy sheet per unit of laminate volume. A previous study [11] on the generation of MIL-HDBK-5 design allowables for fiber/metal laminates has shown the potential feasibility of laminate property as a function of volume fraction. In this study, metal volume fraction of 68.09%, 61.54%, 54.55% (with two different laminate configurations, 3/2 and 5/4), and 50.00% were considered.

4.1 Tension

Forty tensile specimens were tested to determine the values of the tensile ultimate strength, tensile yield strength, and tensile modulus. The data are plotted in Figures 2 through 7. Results show that tensile strength and tensile modulus are linear functions of the aluminum alloy volume fraction. Tensile modulus can be predicted using the ROM, which is the addition of the tensile moduli of the constituents taking into account the thickness of the separate layers. Since the

experimental data of cured glass prepreg are not available, the following back-calculated glass prepreg properties are used in this analysis (which assumes ROM applies): $\sigma_p = 1507$ MPa and $E_p = 22.55$ GPa in the L direction; and $\sigma_p = 742$ MPa and $E_p = 12.43$ GPa in the LT direction. For 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet, we use typical values of $\sigma_{al} = 490$ MPa and $E_{al} = 73.5$ GPa, taken from Reference 13. A comparison between experimental and theoretical prediction from the ROM results of tensile strength and tensile modulus shows in a good agreement as shown in Table 2.

4.2 Compression

Forty compressive specimens were tested to determine the values of the compressive yield strength and compressive modulus. In order to prevent buckling of compression specimen, several layers of GLARE were bonded together prior to testing. All the compression specimens including the unbonded ones were subjected to the same postcure thermal cycle. The data are plotted in Figures 8 through 11. A good linear relationship has been shown to exist between the compressive yield strength and compressive modulus values and the aluminum alloy volume fraction. Compressive modulus can also be predicted by the ROM. The predicted values were obtained using the experimental data of compressive properties of aluminum alloy sheet and cured glass prepreg [14]. They are: $E_p = 38.7$ GPa in the L direction and $E_p = 25.4$ GPa in the LT direction for cross-ply cured glass prepreg; and $E_{al} = 75.8$ GPa for 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet. Experimental results are also in good agreement with the theoretical prediction except for results of the 2/1 lay-up as shown in Table 3.

4.3 In-plane Shear

Forty Iosipescu in-plane shear [15, 16] specimens were tested to determine the values of the shear yield strength and shear modulus. The data are plotted in Figures 12 through 15. A linear relationship is present between shear modulus and aluminum alloy volume fraction. However, the shear yield strength data do not fit well with linear regression model. This suggests that the shear yield strength measured from the Iosipescu shear testing procedure may be underestimated, perhaps due to the shear specimen notch geometry and plasticity of aluminum alloy sheet. Since the experimental data of cured glass prepreg are not available, the following back-calculated glass prepreg properties (assuming ROM applies) are used in the analysis: $G_p = 8.16$ GPa and 8.10 GPa for both the L and LT directions, respectively. For 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet, we use $G_{al} = 27.58$ GPa taken from Reference 13. Comparison between experimental and predicted in-plane shear properties except for results of the 2/1 lay-up are found to be in a good agreement and are listed in Table 4.

4.4 Bearing

Forty bearing specimens having a constant edge distance to pin diameter ratio (e/D) of 3 and width to pin diameter ratio (W/D) of 6 recommended from previous research [17, 18] were tested. A modified ASTM D-953 bearing testing procedure with lateral constraint [19] was employed in this study. The bearing yield strength, bearing ultimate strength at 4% pin hole deformation, and bearing ultimate strength at maximum load were recorded. The data are plotted in Figures 16 through 21. Results show that bearing strength is a function of aluminum alloy volume fraction, although some of scatter exists. Since we do not have the experimental bearing ultimate strength

data for cured glass prepreg, back-calculated glass prepreg properties (assuming ROM applies) are used in this analysis. They are: $\sigma_p = 953$ MPa in the L direction and $\sigma_p = 1033$ MPa in the LT direction. For 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheet, we use $\sigma_{al} = 959$ MPa obtained from Reference 19. A comparison of the experimental and predicted bearing ultimate strength are presented in Table 5. Comparison between experimental and predicted values show in a good agreement in bearing ultimate strength.

In general, for the above four tests, measured mechanical properties of the cured composite prepreg and aluminum alloy sheet used in the laminate should be used for theoretical prediction. In this text, due to budget and time constraints, we only used the back-calculated and typical values, respectively, for the work. In order to arrive at an accurate prediction, test work on laminate components (aluminum alloy sheet and cured prepreg) should be performed in the future.

4.5 Statistical Analysis

All the data populations fit a normal distribution well. This can be seen from the results of Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness-of-fit listed in Table 6. Linear regression analysis has been used for determining the relationship between mechanical properties and aluminum alloy volume fraction. Figures 2 through 21 show that most of the mechanical properties of fiber/metal laminates are a function of aluminum alloy volume fraction. Test hypothesis on linearity has been analyzed through lack-of-goodness-fit. Details of statistical analysis show good linearity at 95% confidence intervals for all properties except shear yield strength. Properties obtained from the same aluminum alloy volume fraction (54.55%) whose panels fabricated from lay-up of 3/2 (using 0.012-in. aluminum alloy sheet) or 5/4 (using 0.012-in. and 0.016-in. aluminum alloy sheets) are shown not to be statistically different. However, the power of statistical testing to discern differences is extremely low due to the small sample sizes involved. Box and whisker plots for each set of data with 95% confidence intervals for factor means show that, for many properties, differences do exist between the two lay-ups containing 54.55% volume fraction of aluminum.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This pilot study of research has concluded that metal volume fraction approach using the rule-of-mixtures may be able to predict most of the mechanical properties of fiber/metal laminates. However, more study is needed to completely verify this concept. If this hypothesis can be well validated, qualifying a fiber/metal laminate family will only require evaluation of a few configurations.

6. FUTURE WORK

Further study for verifying this concept is recommended. Before generating this research, mechanical properties of the cured composite prepreg and aluminum alloy sheet used in the laminates should be experimentally determined. Also, all the failure modes corresponding to different types of tests should be considered in the study. If we can carry out this test program, a validation on the MIL-HDBK-5 type design allowable property prediction will then be characterized and qualified.

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Table 1. Material Descriptions of GLARE 4 Laminates

Lay-up	Total Metal Thickness, in.	Total Laminate Thickness,* in.	Metal Volume Fraction, %
2/1	2 x 0.016	0.047	68.09
3/2	3 x 0.016	0.078	61.54
3/2	3 x 0.012	0.066	54.55
5/4	2 x 0.012 and 3 x 0.016	0.132	54.55
5/4	5 x 0.012	0.120	50.00

*Each cross-ply 0°/90°/0° glass prepreg has a 0.015-in. thickness

Table 2. Comparison between Experimental and Predicted Tensile Properties for GLARE-4 Laminates

Layup	Metal Fraction, %	Longitudinal					Long-Transverse				
		TYS ¹ , MPa	TUS ² _{exp} , MPa	TUS ³ _{rom} , MPa	E ⁴ _{exp} , GPa	E ⁵ _{rom} , GPa	TYS ¹ , MPa	TUS ² _{exp} , MPa	TUS ³ _{rom} , MPa	E ⁴ _{exp} , GPa	E ⁵ _{rom} , GPa
5/4	50.00	321	999	998	49.26	48.03	229	618	616	42.79	42.97
5/4	54.55	333	959	952	50.78	50.34	233	609	605	47.48	45.74
3/2	54.55	316	944	952	50.34	50.34	229	609	605	44.15	45.74
3/2	61.45	334	878	881	53.11	53.90	247	592	587	51.86	50.01
2/1	68.09	341	817	815	56.69	57.24	255	558	570	52.49	54.01

- ¹TYS - Average experimental tensile yield strength
- ²TUS_{exp} - Average experimental tensile ultimate strength
- ³TUS_{rom} - Predicted tensile ultimate strength using rule-of-mixtures
- ⁴E_{exp} - Average experimental tensile modulus
- ⁵E_{rom} - Predicted tensile modulus using rule-of-mixtures

Table 3. Comparison between Experimental and Predicted Compressive Properties for GLARE 4 Laminates

Layup	Metal Fraction, %	Longitudinal			Long-Transverse		
		CYS ¹ , MPa	E _{exp} ² , MPa	E _{rom} ³ , GPa	CYS ¹ , MPa	E _{exp} ² , MPa	E _{rom} ³ , GPa
5/4	50.00	314	59.87	57.25	261	51.68	50.60
5/4	54.55	309	59.67	58.94	268	55.23	52.89
3/2	54.55	327	58.59	58.94	261	52.93	52.89
3/2	61.54	306	63.42	61.53	280	61.56	56.42
2/1	68.09	303	70.04	63.96	289	63.95	59.72

- ¹CYS - Average compressive yield strength
²E_{exp} - Average experimental compressive modulus
³E_{rom} - Predicted compressive modulus using rule-of-mixture

Table 4. Comparison between Experimental and Predicted In-plane Shear Properties for GLARE 4 Laminates

Layup	Metal Fraction, %	Longitudinal			Long-Transverse		
		SYS ¹ , MPa	G _{exp} ² , MPa	G _{rom} ³ , GPa	SYS ¹ , MPa	E _{exp} ² , MPa	G _{rom} ³ , GPa
5/4	50.00	95	11.38	12.59	96	11.55	12.52
5/4	54.55	101	13.67	13.25	98	13.84	13.18
3/2	54.55	100	11.91	13.25	98	11.31	13.18
3/2	61.54	105	15.26	14.40	107	14.33	14.33
2/1	68.09	119	16.77	15.68	117	17.50	15.61

- ¹SYS - Average shear yield strength
²G_{exp} - Average experimental shear modulus
³G_{rom} - Predicted shear modulus using rule-of-mixture

Table 5. Comparison between Experimental and Predicted Bearing Properties for GLARE 4 Laminates

Layup	Metal Fraction, %	Longitudinal			Long-Transverse		
		BYS ¹ , MPa	BUS _{exp} ² -max, MPa	BUS _{rom} ³ , GPa	BYS ¹ , MPa	BUS _{exp} ² -max, MPa	BUS _{rom} ³ , GPa
5/4	50.00	617	903	956	579	942	996
5/4	54.55	625	896	956	542	928	993
3/2	54.55	653	945	956	598	971	993
3/2	61.54	668	983	957	577	1008	988
2/1	68.09	667	1020	957	627	1061	983

- ¹BYS - Average bearing yield strength
²BUS_{exp}-max - Average experimental bearing ultimate strength determined at maximum failure
³BUS_{rom} - Predicted bearing ultimate strength using rule-of-mixture

Table 6. Test for Adequacy of the Simple Regression Analysis and Distribution Fitting Function for GLARE 4 Laminates

Property vs. Metal Fraction	TYS (L)	TUS (L)	E ₁ (L)	TYS (LT)	TUS (LT)	E ₁ (LT)	CYS (L)
Probability Level (Lack-of-Goodness-Fit)	0.91785	0.92905	0.81278	0.09203	0.08348	0.75008	0.92369
Linearity of Relationship	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Sig. Level of K-S ¹ Test for Normal Distribution	0.76716	0.6519	0.75823	0.21529	0.65687	0.76675	0.77935
Normality of Data	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

E _c (L)	CYS (LT)	E _c (LT)	SYS (L)	G ₃ (L)	SYS (T)	G ₃ (LT)	BYS (L)	BUS-4% (L)	BUS-max (L)
0.58925	0.54426	0.17687	0.00001	0.66312	0.00652	0.38853	0.30664	0.25612	0.48224
yes	yes	yes	no	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
0.48434	0.88405	0.38086	0.35648	0.54822	0.17336	0.78237	0.98868	0.898	0.88176
yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

BYS (LT)	BUS-4% (LT)	BUS-max (LT)
0.19931	0.25785	0.24305
yes	yes	yes
0.98687	0.49504	0.59557
yes	yes	yes

¹K-S: Test of Kolmogorov-Smirnov for goodness-of-fit

Figure 1. Fiber/Metal Structural Laminates (Typical 3/2 Lay-Up Shown)

Figure 2: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Tensile Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 4: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Tensile Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 3: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Tensile Ultimate Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 5: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Tensile Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 6: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Tensile Ultimate Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 8: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Compressive Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 7: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Tensile Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 9: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Compressive Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 10: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Compressive Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 12: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Shear Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 11: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Compressive Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 13: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Shear Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 14: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Shear Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 16: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Bearing Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 15: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Shear Modulus Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 17: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Bearing Ultimate Strength at 4% Pin-hole Deformation Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 18: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Longitudinal Bearing Ultimate Strength at Maximum Failure Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 20: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Bearing Ultimate Strength at 4% Pin-hole Deformation Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 19: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Bearing Yield Strength Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction

Figure 21: 95% Confidence Intervals for GLARE 4 Laminate Long-transverse Bearing Ultimate Strength at Maximum Failure Variation with Aluminum Volume Fraction